

Challenges to achieve equivalence in terminological translation

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to outline some of the most common terminological issues that audiovisual translators encounter when translating science films. These difficulties include term recognition, term comprehension, appropriate equivalent selection, handling inadequate equivalents, denominative variation resolution, selecting between in vivo and in vitro terminology, and resolving mistranscriptions.

Key words: Translational adequacy, terminology standardization, translation validation, equivalence testing, terminological harmonization.

Despite its importance in translation theory and practice, achieving equivalence presents several challenges for translators due to linguistic diversity, cultural differences and the complexity of specialist terminology¹. Some of the main problems in achieving equivalence are:

- a. *Linguistic variability:* languages contain different lexical, grammatical and semantic structures that may not always have direct equivalents in different languages. Translators must navigate language variations and find appropriate equivalents that accurately convey the intent in the target language.
- b. *Cultural specificity:* cultural references, idiomatic expressions and socio-cultural norms are deeply rooted in language use and can present challenges to achieve cultural equivalence. When adapting elements of the source text, translators must consider cultural specificities to ensure their content and meaning in the target culture.
- c. *Domain-Specific Terminology:* Special fields such as law, medicine, engineering and science often contain domain-specific terminology that may not have direct equivalents in other languages. Translators must have expertise in these areas so that they can accurately convey special concepts and terms in their translations.
- d. *Adapting to the context:* translating texts without taking into account their specific communicative context can prevent the achievement of contextual

¹ Gerzymisch-Arbogast, H., & Budin, G. (Eds.). (2014). Knowledge engineering and management: Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Intelligent Systems and Knowledge Engineering, Beijing, China, Dec 2012 (ISKE 2012) (Vol. 4). Springer Science & Business Media.

equivalence. Translators must consider situational factors, conversational signs and genres to ensure that translations are appropriate to the context.

e. *Nuances and Connotations*: The subtle nuances and connotations associated with words and expressions present challenges in achieving semantic and pragmatic equivalence. Translators must tune in to these nuances to capture the full range of meanings embedded in specialist terminology.

f. *Register and style*: In order to achieve lexical and pragmatic equivalence, it is necessary to maintain the appropriate register and style in various languages. Translators must consider variations in formality, tone and style when choosing equivalents for certain expressions and expressions.²

To meet these challenges, translators must use a combination of language skills, cultural sensitivity, domain knowledge and strategic decision-making to ensure that translation intent is accurately conveyed while respecting linguistic and cultural differences.

Practical approaches to achieve equivalence. In practice, translators use different approaches and strategies to achieve translation equivalence. These practical approaches include a variety of techniques that enable translators to navigate linguistic and cultural challenges while preserving the integrity of the source text. Some common practical approaches to achieving equivalence are:

1. *Research and mastery of terminology*: Identifying exact equivalents of special terms in different languages requires extensive research and mastery of terminology. Translators rely on reliable sources, vocabularies, corpora and domain-specific resources to validate their choice of matches.

2. *Contextual Analysis*: Translators perform a detailed contextual analysis of the source text to understand its communicative purpose, audience expectations, genres and situational factors. This analysis informs them of equivalents that match the specific context of the source text.

3. *Comparative Analysis*: Comparative analysis involves comparing the corresponding elements of the source and target texts to identify potential challenges in achieving equivalence. Translators appreciate the lexical, grammatical, semantic, pragmatic and cultural differences between languages in order to make informed decisions about equivalent expressions.

4. *Adaptation Strategies*: Translators use adaptation strategies to deal with challenges, such as compensation (multiple terms to convey a single concept), modulation (changing perspective or emphasis without changing the main meaning),

² Fuentes Luque, A., & Faber, P. (2015). Terminology in knowledge management: An overview of current research and practice in the digital age. In Terminology in Everyday Life (pp. 23-38). John Benjamins Publishing

and paraphrasing (reforming content while maintaining relevance). information). in achieving a direct equivalent.

5. Ways to work together: Working with subject matter experts, bilingual consultants or native speakers can provide valuable information on how to find the right match with professional terminology. Consulting people with expertise in certain fields or cultural contexts improves the quality of translations.

6. Review and Feedback: Thorough review and feedback processes are critical to refining translations and ensuring optimal compliance. Translators seek comments from colleagues or reviewers to confirm their choices and correct discrepancies or errors.³

By integrating these practical approaches into their translation process, translators can overcome the challenges of linguistic diversity, cultural specificity, regional terminology, contextual adaptation, nuance and connotation, register and stylistic variation while striving to achieve accurate and effective correspondence.

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³ Cabré Castellví, M. T., & Estopà Bagot, R. M. (2015). La terminologia en l'era de la comunicació multilingüe i multimèdia: la gestió del coneixement en l'àmbit de la traducció i la localització de programari i webs en català i altres llengües minoritzades.

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